

Editorial

Sex- and Country-Based Authorship Representation in the Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health: Statistics for 2023/2024.

The Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health (JCTH) is committed to fostering a diverse and inclusive research community. As part of this commitment, we regularly analyse authorship data to assess sex and geographical representation. This editorial presents an overview of the sex and country-based authorship statistics for articles published in the JCTH during 2023 and 2024.

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Sex representation

The percentage of female authors has steadily increased over the years in several fields. However, several reports still point to an unbalanced ratio, with male authors still being the majority¹⁻³.

As can be observed in Figure 1, female authors were dominant in the first two years of the JCTH's publications (2023/2024). From 2023 to 2024, there was an increase in female authors from 66% to 89%, meaning that male authors were underrepresented, countering general trends in many research fields.

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Country Representation

The JCTH welcomes submissions from researchers worldwide. We are committed to promoting international collaboration and diversity in research. By publishing research from a variety of countries, we pretend to reflect the global nature of complementary therapies in health. According to Figure 2, there is a clear dominance of Portuguese nationals publishing in the JCTH with 90% of authors coming from this country (in 2023 and 2024).

This rate is perceived as natural since the JCTH has several research connections with organizations from this country for the organization of scientific events such as the International Congress held in 2023⁴ and the Portuguese Symposium in 2024⁵. Therefore, despite being an International Journal, the JCTH has started being known in this geographical area. With 10%, Brazil, Spain and China are the other represented countries.

Future Directions

To further promote diversity and inclusion, the JCTH will continue to encourage submissions from underrepresented groups.

We will actively seek submissions from researchers from diverse backgrounds, including male and female authors, minority groups, and researchers from low- and middle-income countries.

As well, there is also the need to study sex representation in the research field of complementary therapies to better understand the tendencies observed in this analysis.

With this report, the JCTH will be able to create strategies to allow a more equitable and inclusive research environment and to advance the field of complementary therapies in health.

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